

Cybersecurity and Medical Imaging: A Simulation-Based Approach to DICOM Communication

Stylianios Karagiannis^{1,2,*}

¹ PDMFC, R. Fradesso da Silveira, 4-1B, 1300-609 Lisboa, Portugal

² Department of Informatics, Ionian University, Plateia Tsirigoti 7, 49100 Corfu, Greece

³ Hospital do Espírito Santo de Évora, EPE, Largo Senhor da Pobreza, 7000-811 Évora, Portugal

⁴ Centre for Secure, Intelligent and Usable Systems (CSIUS), School of Sport & Health Sciences, University of Brighton, Brighton BN2 4AT, UK

* Correspondence: stylianos.karagiannis@pdmfc.com or skaragiannis@ionio.gr

† These authors contributed equally to this work.

Abstract: Medical imaging plays a crucial role in modern healthcare, providing essential information for accurate diagnoses and treatment planning. The Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) standard has revolutionized the storage, transmission, and sharing of medical images and related data. Despite its advantages, the implementation and deployment of the DICOM protocol often suffer from incomplete understanding, leading to vulnerabilities within the healthcare ecosystem. This research paper presents an implementation of the DICOM communication and the development of a practical demonstration for simulation purposes [1]. The simulation can be used for conducting cybersecurity tests in the context of DICOM communication. Overall, the simulation can provide the digital environment for retrieving valuable insights into the practical aspects of DICOM communication and PACS integration, serving as a valuable resource for medical imaging professionals, researchers, and developers. Therefore, the research results provide practical insights, while the DICOM simulation can be used in realistic contexts to showcase various security scenarios.

Keywords: Medical imaging; DICOM; PACS; eHealth; Simulation

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1. Introduction

Medical imaging is of utmost importance in modern healthcare for accurate diagnoses and treatment planning [2–8]. DICOM, a widely used standard, has revolutionized the storage, transmission, and sharing of medical images and associated data [9–12]. DICOM stands for "Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine" and it is a widely used standard for the communication, storage, and management of medical images [13]. DICOM enables interoperability among various medical imaging devices and systems, ensuring that medical images and associated data can be easily exchanged and interpreted across different vendors and institutions. As part of the DICOM infrastructure, the Picture Archiving and Communication System (PACS) plays a key role in enabling the storage, retrieval, and distribution of medical images and the associated information [14,15].

Past attacks targeting DICOM systems have exposed vulnerabilities in the security infrastructure of medical imaging technology [16]. These attacks highlight the need for heightened security measures in safeguarding sensitive patient data and maintaining the integrity of medical images. For example, in 2017, researchers from Massachusetts General Hospital identified thousands of unprotected DICOM servers globally, with hundreds in the United States, revealing patient information [17]. Similarly, in 2018, a security researcher employed an Internet scanning tool to access unprotected DICOM servers and even produced a 3D model of an individual's anatomy [18]. These incidents underscore the urgency of implementing robust security protocols, including encryption, authentication, network segmentation, and regular security audits, to mitigate risks and protect patient privacy within the DICOM ecosystem.

Despite the indispensability of DICOM and PACS, there is often a lack of comprehensive understanding and implementation in healthcare organizations [19,20]. This lack of comprehension and implementation can lead to various security challenges and vulnerabilities [21,22]. The existing literature highlights the security vulnerabilities in these systems, such as unencrypted communications, weak authentication mechanisms, and inadequate access controls [16,23–25]. Nevertheless, healthcare organizations often fail to implement robust security measures and conduct comprehensive security testing, leaving them vulnerable to cyberattacks [26,27].

This research paper proposes a DICOM simulation in order to improve the understanding of DICOM network protocol. The simulation serves as a practical demonstration to enhance comprehension and implementation. By simulating the data transfer using the DICOM protocol from a healthcare modality, the practical aspects of DICOM communication and PACS integration can be further investigated. The simulation involves the replication of the network layer for DICOM transfers and establishing the necessary connections to a PACS server.

1.1. Contribution

The research paper makes significant contributions to the field of medical imaging by providing a practical demonstration of DICOM data transfer in a medical imaging environment. The code is uploaded on GitHub [1] and the key contributions of the research paper are as follows:

- Present a practical demonstration of data transfer in a medical imaging environment by simulating the DICOM data transfer in a virtual environment. This demonstration provides the environment for a better understanding of DICOM communication and the integration of PACS in a realistic setting.
- Provide step-by-step implementation and code snippets that serve as a valuable resource for education and learning in order to have a better understanding of DICOM communication and PACS integration.
- The simulation offers a digital environment that enables hands-on experience of a realistic implementation for DICOM communication and PACS integration. This allows the interaction with the simulated environment.
- The simulated environment can be utilized as a valuable asset for security and privacy tests. By simulating DICOM transfers and PACS integration, common and critical vulnerabilities can be uncovered and conduct comprehensive security testing to address cybersecurity concerns in medical imaging systems.

1.2. Related Work

Several works have contributed to understanding DICOM communication and PACS integration in medical imaging. Zhou et al. [28] identified a lack of tools for PACS training and developed a Radiology Information System (RIS) simulator. However, advancements in medical imaging, DICOM communication, PACS integration, and cybersecurity have occurred since then. Coutinho et al. [22] introduced a cybersecurity methodology and tools for healthcare operational information systems, focusing on cybersecurity. Furthermore, the researchers used Orthanc [29] and ONIS [30]. Similarly, other researchers provided extensively details the advantages of the Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) protocol while outlining a user-friendly approach for individuals who are new to this concept [31].

Instead, in this research paper, a DICOM simulator was developed in a virtual lab context for conducting security tests. The study places emphasis on in-depth analyses and learning aspects related to the fundamental attributes of the DICOM protocol, and the approach remains flexible for subsequent extensions, open for utilization by researchers according to their requirements.

Potter et al. [32] discussed the significance of the DICOM Validation Toolkit (DVTK) [33], which offers potential for individuals working with the DICOM standard. Other

researchers [34] also utilized DVTK and highlighted the benefits of a HIS, RIS, and PACS system in healthcare management. Additionally, Oemig et al. [35] presented a collection of tools, including DVTK [33] and HAPI [36], to explore DICOM software development and its integration with PACS. Mantri et al. [37] conducted a comparative study of DICOM API libraries, while NIST [38] identified software and managed risks within the PACS ecosystem. Mileva et al. [39] introduced covert channels for DICOM transport mechanisms, offering possibilities for covert communications, data exfiltration, and privacy leaking attacks.

Paper	Main Focus	Contribution of DICOM simulation
[28]	Lack of tools for practical PACS training.	Comprehensive demonstration of DICOM data transfer within a medical imaging environment. It offers step-by-step implementation guidance and code snippets, enabling a better understanding of DICOM communication and integration with PACS systems.
[22]	Focus primarily on cybersecurity methodology.	The simulation serves as a controlled environment for conducting security assessments related to DICOM data transfer, offering a unique contribution by merging simulation with cybersecurity considerations.
[32]	Emphasis on the DICOM Validation Toolkit (DVTK).	Offers detailed Python library implementations that focus on fundamental DICOM communication concepts. Notably, it provides adaptable code that can be tailored to specific use-case requirements.
[35]	Exploration of DICOM software development and integration.	Enhances the practicality of training for medical imaging professionals, offering a contribution that bridges the gap between software development and medical imaging.
[37]	Comparative study of DICOM API libraries.	Practical understanding of data exchange, adding value by examining and by using DICOM APIs in a simulated environment.
[38]	Identification of risks within the PACS ecosystem.	Establish a practical baseline environment for comprehending and addressing security concerns in DICOM systems, offering valuable insights into risk identification.
[39]	Introduction of covert channels for DICOM transport mechanisms.	Extends the understanding of potential vulnerabilities and hidden pathways within DICOM communication.

Table 1. Comparison between the related work and DICOM simulation

Table 1 showcases the comprehensive differentiations and additions from the existing pertinent research. Within this study, a DICOM simulation and a topology is introduced, showcasing the interaction between DICOM and PACS. The study is valuable to a broader audience interested in DICOM communication, and the practical application of DICOM simulations in real-world scenarios for learning and testing purposes.

1.3. Paper Structure

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Section 3 presents the methodology employed to develop the DICOM simulation software. Section 4 provides details on the implementation and explanation of the Python code. Simulation results, validation, and analysis reports are provided in Section 5 along with a further explanation of the DICOM protocol. The research paper concludes in Section 6 with potential future avenues of this research.

2. Background

DICOM defines a set of entities representing different aspects of medical imaging and patient information [40].

- **Patients (P):** Encapsulates individual patient data, including attributes like name, ID, and birthdate. A patient p can be associated with one or more studies ($P \rightarrow [S_1, S_2, \dots]$)
- **Study and Study Series (S and Se):** Includes related medical images and metadata, while Series groups images within a study based on common characteristics. A study s can include one or more series ($Se = [S_1, S_2, \dots]$)
- **Image (I):** Set of DICOM images I . Series Se groups related images ($Se \rightarrow [I_1, I_2, \dots]$).
- **Physician (Ph):** Represents healthcare professionals. The images I are interpreted by a physician Ph ($Ph \rightarrow [I_1, I_2, \dots]$).
- **Modalities (M):** Refers to imaging-related equipment or healthcare modalities. Pertains to imaging devices used, specifying manufacturer details and software version. Images I are generated by a specific modality M ($M \rightarrow [I_1, I_2, \dots]$)

DICOM is designed for the management of medical images and associated data within a healthcare environment.

2.1. Picture Archiving and Communication System (PACS)

PACS is a crucial system utilized in the medical field for the storage, management, and distribution of medical images and associated patient information. It replaces traditional film-based systems by enabling healthcare providers to capture, store, retrieve, and view medical images electronically. With PACS, the cumbersome task of managing physical film records is replaced by a digital infrastructure that facilitates easy image access and promotes efficient collaboration among healthcare professionals. Orthanc [29,41], on the other hand, is an open-source implementation of a PACS server. It provides a lightweight, vendor-neutral, and standards-compliant solution for managing medical images and associated data. Orthanc serves as a software platform that can be utilized to establish a PACS server infrastructure. Its open-source nature offers flexibility and customization options, making it an appealing choice for institutions and developers seeking to create their own PACS environment.

2.2. Encoding and Compression Techniques in DICOM

The Transfer Syntax [42] in DICOM refers to the encoding and compression techniques used to represent and transmit DICOM data. It determines how the DICOM objects, including images, are serialized into a byte stream that can be transmitted or stored. DICOM supports multiple Transfer Syntaxes to provide flexibility, interoperability, and efficient handling of various data formats. Some commonly used Transfer Syntaxes in DICOM include the following [42]:

- **Implicit VR Little Endian:** Implicit VR Little Endian is a Transfer Syntax that uses a combination of implicit value representation encoding and little-endian byte ordering. It is widely used for uncompressed DICOM images and supports a variety of data types. It is the default Transfer Syntax for most DICOM files.
- **Explicit VR Little Endian:** Explicit VR Little Endian is a Transfer Syntax that uses explicit VR encoding and little-endian byte ordering. It is also commonly used for uncompressed DICOM images. It provides explicit VR tags, which make it easier to parse and understand the data.
- **JPEG Lossless:** JPEG Lossless [13,42] is a Transfer Syntax that employs the Joint Photographic Experts Group (JPEG) Baseline algorithm for lossless compression of DICOM images. It is utilized when a balance between compression and preservation of image quality is required. It achieves significant compression ratios while maintaining the integrity of the image data. JPEG Lossless is particularly useful for storing or transmitting DICOM images where lossy compression is not acceptable.

- **JPEG Baseline:** JPEG Baseline [42,43] is a specific Transfer Syntax that utilizes the JPEG Baseline algorithm for compressing DICOM images. It is a lossy compression technique that achieves significant compression ratios while maintaining acceptable image quality for many medical imaging applications. JPEG Baseline is often used for transmitting DICOM images over networks with limited bandwidth or storage capacity, as it helps reduce the size of the image data.

By supporting various Transfer Syntaxes, DICOM enables interoperability between different systems, ensuring that medical imaging data can be exchanged and interpreted correctly across diverse platforms and applications.

2.3. Service-Object Pair (SOP) Class and Transfer Syntax

SOP Classes [42] are service objects that encapsulate the DICOM image files. An SOP Class defines a specific type of medical imaging or non-imaging service that can be performed on a DICOM object. It represents a combination of a service and an object on which the service can be performed. Popular SOP Classes include the following, among others [42]:

- **CT Image Storage (1.2.840.10008.5.1.4.1.1.2):** Used to store Computed Tomography (CT) images. CT images are used for diagnostic purposes and provide detailed cross-sectional views of the body.
- **MR Image Storage (1.2.840.10008.5.1.4.1.1.4):** Used to store Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) images. MRI images are used to visualize internal structures of the body using magnetic fields and radio waves, providing detailed anatomical information.
- **Ultrasound Image Storage (1.2.840.10008.5.1.4.1.1.6.1):** Used to store ultrasound images. Ultrasound imaging uses high-frequency sound waves to generate images of organs and tissues in real-time, often used in obstetrics, cardiology, and other medical applications.
- **X-Ray Radiography Image Storage (1.2.840.10008.5.1.4.1.1.1):** Used to store X-ray images. X-ray images are widely used for various medical purposes, providing two-dimensional images that help diagnose bone fractures, detect abnormalities, and visualize internal structures.

These above SOP Classes define the necessary metadata, attributes, and operations required to handle and interpret images of their respective modalities.

2.4. Presentation Contexts

Presentation Contexts in DICOM define the combination of a specific SOP Class and one or more supported Transfer Syntaxes that an AE can handle for communication purposes. When two DICOM devices establish a connection or association, they negotiate the set of services and data formats that they can support. This negotiation is done using Presentation Contexts. A Presentation Context consists of the following components [42]:

- **Abstract Syntax:** The Abstract Syntax identifies the class or type of DICOM object being transmitted or requested. It represents a specific SOP Class, such as CT Image Storage or MR Image Storage.
- **Transfer Syntaxes:** Transfer Syntaxes define the encoding and compression techniques used to represent and transmit the DICOM data. They specify how the DICOM object will be serialized into a byte stream. Multiple Transfer Syntaxes can be associated with a single Abstract Syntax to allow flexibility in data formats and compression options.

The process of association negotiation in the context of medical imaging involves the exchange of information between two devices. During this negotiation, both devices share a list of supported Presentation Contexts. Each Presentation Context is composed of an Abstract Syntax along with one or more Transfer Syntaxes that the device is capable of supporting for that specific Abstract Syntax.

The two devices then compare the lists of Presentation Contexts they have shared and work towards finding a mutually supported Presentation Context. Once this mutual

agreement is reached, it signifies that the devices can effectively communicate and conduct operations involving DICOM objects. They do so using the designated Abstract Syntax, and the agreed-upon Transfer Syntax is employed for the communication.

For instance, consider a scenario where two devices establish a Presentation Context with an Abstract Syntax. This agreement indicates that the devices are now equipped to exchange and manipulate magnetic resonance image data using the JPEG Baseline compression algorithm. This enables seamless and efficient communication between the devices while ensuring compatibility in handling medical image information.

2.5. Application Entities (AE)

AE [42] is a fundamental concept in the Digital Imaging and DICOM standard. It represents a node or device in a network that communicates using DICOM protocols. An AE can be a piece of medical imaging equipment, such as a CT scanner, MRI machine, or a PACS server. In the context of DICOM, an AE is identified by a unique AE title, which serves as its network address. The AE title is used to establish connections and enable communication between different entities in a DICOM network. Each AE is responsible for sending and receiving DICOM objects, which include medical images, patient information, and related metadata.

AE provides services such as query/retrieve, storage, and printing of DICOM objects. It can act as a Service Class Provider (SCP), which receives requests for services, or a Service Class User (SCU) [42], which initiates requests and interacts with other endpoints. The roles of SCP and SCU can be performed by the same AE or different endpoints, depending on the system architecture and requirements. An Application Entity represents a DICOM node or device in the network. In the DICOM simulator, an AE is created using the AE class from *Pynetdicom*. The AE title is set to "MODALITY", which identifies the simulated modality in the network.

3. Methodology

This section provides an in-depth explanation of the methodology used to implement the DICOM simulator in Python. It outlines the key steps involved in establishing communication with the PACS server, configuring the necessary libraries, and sending DICOM images. To understand the interactions between DICOM modalities and PACS servers, a mathematical model can be formulated to describe the association between DICOM modalities and PACS servers.

The association between a DICOM modality and a PACS server involves several parameters that define the communication and data exchange. Let's consider a DICOM modality, M , and a PACS server. The relationship between M and PACS can be represented using the mathematical equation (1).

$$A(M, S) = \{AE_M, AE_{PACS}, SOP_{class}, TS\} \quad (1)$$

where $A(M, S)$ represents the association between modality M and PACS server $PACS$. AE_M is the Application Entity representing the DICOM modality in the network. AE_S is the Application Entity representing the PACS server in the network. SOP_{class} denotes the SOP Class, specifying the type of medical image or information being exchanged. TS is the transfer syntax that defines how data is encoded and decoded during transmission.

Application Entities (AE) can be represented as nodes in a network graph. Each node corresponds to an AE, which can be either the DICOM modality or the PACS server. The communication between these nodes is facilitated by the DICOM protocol, as presented in the equation (2). The equation (2) describes nodes and edges, as the elements of a graph, where AE_M and AE_S are nodes, representing entities within a network, and the edge (AE_M, AE_S) signifies a connection or relationship between these nodes.

$$\text{Nodes: } N = \{AE_M, AE_S\} \text{ and Edges: } E = \{(AE_M, AE_S)\} \quad (2)$$

where N is the set of nodes, representing the DICOM modality and PACS server. E is the set of edges, indicating the communication link between the modality and the server.

SOP classes define the type of medical image or object being exchanged, while transfer syntax specifies how data is encoded and compressed for transmission. The association of SOP classes and transfer syntax is presented in equation (3).

$$A(SOP_{class}, TS) = \{SOP_{class}, TS\} \quad (3)$$

where A is the function that takes two parameters: SOP_{class} and TS . SOP_{class} represents a parameter related to the class of SOP in the context of DICOM. Similarly, TS represents the Transfer Syntax in DICOM. SOP_{class} represents the specific type of medical image or information. TS denotes the transfer syntax used for encoding and decoding. The function A in equation (3), takes two DICOM-related parameters and constructs a set containing those parameters' values.

DICOM communication often involves sensitive patient data, necessitating secure protocols [44]. Transport Layer Security (TLS) and Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) ensure encrypted data transmission and authentication and Internet Protocol Security (IPsec) offers secure network layer communication. DICOM Secure Communication Profiles define secure communication guidelines, enhancing data privacy and integrity in medical imaging networks. The choice of protocol depends on security needs, regulatory compliance, and infrastructure compatibility. The dependency graph (Figure 1) depicts the DICOM architecture that was followed by this research. These concepts, although briefly summarized in this section, will be explored in greater depth later on, shedding light on their profound influence within the field of medical imaging.

Figure 1. Dependency graph for the DICOM/PACS communication

At the core of DICOM is the AE, which designates network-connected devices, such as imaging systems or workstations (Figure 1) or healthcare modalities. Playing a crucial role in simplifying accessibility for healthcare professionals, PACS servers are responsible for the storage, retrieval, and orchestration of medical images and their associated data.

The SOP Classes play a categorical role in delineating various types of medical studies or objects, each tailored to specific imaging modalities, such as CT scanners or MRI. They detail the required attributes and structural elements crucial for accurate representation of data. Intimately connected to this are the concepts of Transfer Syntaxes, which encompass

the encoding principles governing the compression and formatting of DICOM data. These principles ensure seamless interoperability across a diverse array of devices.

During communication, Presentation Contexts come into play by establishing agreements between devices regarding the supported SOP Classes and Transfer Syntaxes for the duration of the communication session. These fundamental concepts, intricate in their complexity and significant in their role, are poised for a more profound exploration later in this section.

As presented in Figure 1, to establish the association between the AE and the PACS, the research employed *Pynetdicom* [45]. *Pynetdicom* is a Python implementation of the DICOM networking protocol that enables communication between different DICOM entities. It provides the necessary functionalities to establish the association, transfer DICOM data, and manage network connections. In terms of data security during transmission, both Orthanc and *Pynetdicom* support encryption. Encryption is a crucial aspect of securing sensitive medical data during transmission to ensure privacy and prevent unauthorized access. The use of encryption adds an extra layer of protection to the data being transferred between the AE and the PACS, reducing the risk of potential security breaches.

3.1. *Pydicom: Modify and Write DICOM Files with Python*

In this research, *Pydicom* [46] was used as a tool to read DICOM files and send them to the Application Entity (AE). The AE supports Presentation Contexts, which consist of SOP classes and transfer syntaxes [39,42,46]. The integration as presented in Figure 1 was focused on the integration between AE and the PACS server.

Pydicom is a widely-used Python library that offers a range of functionalities for working with DICOM files. It is specifically designed to handle DICOM data, allowing users to read, manipulate, and write DICOM files effectively. In the context of the DICOM simulator, *Pydicom* is utilized to read the DICOM files from the local folder and prepare them for transmission to the PACS server. The library provides the necessary tools and functions to parse the DICOM files, extracting relevant information and organizing it into a structured format.

One of the key functions provided by *Pydicom* library is *dcmread()*. This function is used to read and parse DICOM files in Python. It accepts the path or a file-like object of the DICOM file as input and returns a Dataset object. The Dataset object represents the parsed data and contains various attributes and methods to access and manipulate the DICOM information. By utilizing the *dcmread()* function, the DICOM simulator can read the DICOM files and extract the required information, such as patient data, imaging parameters, and study details. This information can then be utilized to simulate the transmission of DICOM data to the PACS server.

3.2. *Pynetdicom: A Python Implementation of the DICOM Networking Protocol*

Pynetdicom is a Python library that implements the DICOM network protocol and enables communication between DICOM applications. It provides functionalities to establish associations between DICOM nodes and facilitates the sending and receiving of DICOM data. In the context of the DICOM simulator, *Pynetdicom* is utilized to establish a connection with the PACS server and transmit DICOM images. The library offers an AE class, which is employed to create an Application Entity representing the local node or device in the simulator. To define the supported presentation contexts, which determine the combination of SOP Classes and Transfer Syntaxes that the AE can handle, the *supported_contexts* attribute of the AE class is set. This attribute specifies the supported DICOM services and protocols.

The *add_requested_context()* method is used to specify additional requested contexts, allowing the AE to indicate the SOP Classes and Transfer Syntaxes it wants to use for communication with the remote DICOM entity. The *associate()* method establishes an association with the PACS server, enabling subsequent data exchange. This method initiates the DICOM association negotiation process, which involves negotiating supported presenta-

tion contexts, transferring the DICOM application context, and verifying the compatibility between the local and remote DICOM entities.

To transmit DICOM datasets to the connected PACS server, the `send_c_store()` method is utilized. This method ensures proper encoding and delivery of the DICOM data. It handles the DICOM C-STORE service, which is responsible for storing DICOM datasets on the PACS server. The `send_c_store()` method provides status codes to indicate the success or failure of the storage request. Finally, the `release()` method is used to terminate the association between DICOM entities. This method initiates a graceful closure of the communication session by sending release request messages to both the local and remote entities.

3.3. Association Establishment Between AE and PACS

In the diagram provided (Figure 2), the deployment of a simulation is illustrated on Host 1. The main process, labeled "Association" is associated with the AE within the simulation. The AE serves as a representation of a device or node within the network, denoted as *AE*. Similarly, the Orthanc PACS server is represented as *PACS*. The initiation of communication between these entities is facilitated by the following method, establishing a connection for seamless data exchange, as defined in equation (4).

$$association_successful = associate(AE, PACS) \quad (4)$$

The success of this initiation is captured by the variable `association_successful`, indicating whether the association process was successful or not. Data transmission, which involves the exchange of medical images and related information, can be visually represented as a flow using directional arrows. This abstraction aids in understanding the dynamic exchange between different components of the system. The connectivity and integrity of the communication link are monitored using the function as presented in equation (5), enabling the verification outcome can be defined as equation (6).

$$status = check_status(modality, PACS) \quad (5)$$

$$association_successful = associate(AE, PACS) \quad (6)$$

Data processing and release encompasses a sequence of operations applied to DICOM data, fulfilling specific tasks within the system. The established communication link between the AE and PACS is vital for seamless data exchange and successful execution of communication operations. Figure 2 visualizes the connection between the simulation and the PACS server, showcasing the flow of DICOM data and communication within the simulated environment. This connection enables the transmission of DICOM images and associated information from the simulation to the PACS server, mimicking real-world scenarios and facilitating the exploration and understanding of DICOM communication and PACS integration.

The simulation involves processing a dataset and initiating a request. The Association process reads the dataset and performs various operations. A status check is applied to verify the connection of the DICOM modality to the PACS server hosted on Host 2. If the connectivity is confirmed, the Association process sends the processed data to the PACS server. Once the data transmission is successful, the Association process releases the connection. Overall, the diagram showcases the flow of data processing and communication between Host 1, the Association process, and the PACS server on Host 2.

To establish a connection with the PACS server, the AE utilizes the `associate()` method from the `Pynetdicom` library. This method serves as a way for the AE to initiate an association with the PACS server, enabling communication between them.

The `associate()` method requires several input parameters, including the IP address and port number of the PACS server, as well as the AE title associated with the PACS server. When this method is invoked, the AE triggers the association process. If the process is successful, it results in the creation of a communication link between the AE and the

Figure 2. Establishment of the association between AE and PACS

PACS server. Once this association is successfully established, the AE gains the ability to effectively interact with the PACS server.

This interaction encompasses various tasks, such as sending and retrieving medical images and the associated data. Leveraging the established connection, the AE can transmit DICOM data objects to the PACS server.

3.4. Encryption

The DICOM simulator provides an option to add a TLS layer for encryption, supported as well by Orthanc. By enabling TLS support in the DICOM simulator, it ensures that the transmission of DICOM data between the simulator and the PACS server is encrypted, thereby enhancing data security. To enable TLS support in ORTHANC, the following steps should be completed:

- **Building a TLS Context:** A TLS context needs to be created within ORTHANC. The TLS context defines the configuration and settings for the TLS encryption.
- **Loading the Necessary Certificate and Private Key:** To establish secure communication, a valid TLS certificate, and its corresponding private key need to be provided. The TLS certificate is obtained from a trusted Certificate Authority (CA) and serves as proof of identity for the server.
- **Adding the Supported Context with the TLS Context to the AE:** In Orthanc, an AE represents a network entity that can communicate using the DICOM protocol. The TLS context is then added to the AE configuration, associating the TLS encryption capabilities with the AE.

By completing these steps and configuring the TLS settings correctly, the DICOM simulator with TLS support ensures that DICOM data transmitted between the simulator and the PACS server is encrypted. This encryption helps protect the confidentiality and integrity of the data during transmission, mitigating the risk of unauthorized access or tampering.

4. Implementation

This section provides detailed insights into the implementation of the DICOM simulator, focusing on the necessary configurations, setting up the environment, and the steps involved in establishing communication with the PACS server and sending DICOM images.

4.1. Setting up the Python Libraries

Before implementing the DICOM simulator, it is essential to set up and install the required libraries: *Pydicom* and *Pynetdicom*. The provided code is written in Python and

demonstrates a function for sending DICOM files to a PACS server. Providing a pip requirements file or setting up an isolated environment can also be streamlined using services like Docker [47], which simplifies the environment setup process and ensures enhanced portability[1]. An extended explanation of the code follows in the code listing below.

Listing 1: Importing the libraries

```

1 import os
2 from pydicom import dcmread
3 from pydicom.uid import JPEG Baseline
4 from pynetdicom import AE, StoragePresentationContexts
5 from pynetdicom.sop_class import CTImageStorage

```

In Listing 1 the necessary modules and classes required for the code are imported. *os* is imported to perform file operations, *dcmread* is imported from the *Pydicom* library for reading DICOM files, *JPEG Baseline* is imported from *pydicom.uid* for specifying the transfer syntax, *AE* and *StoragePresentationContexts* are imported from *Pynetdicom* for managing the application entity and storage presentation contexts, and *CTImageStorage* is imported from *pynetdicom.sop_class* for specifying the DICOM storage context.

Listing 2: The main function

```

1 def send_dicom_to_pacs(dicom_folder, pacs_ip, pacs_port, pacs_ae_title):
2     # Create an Application Entity
3     ae = AE(ae_title='MODALITY')
4     ae.supported_contexts = StoragePresentationContexts
5
6     # Add the requested transfer syntax for the X-Ray Angiographic ↵
7     # Image Storage contextae.add_requested_context↵
8     ('1.2.840.10008.5.1.4.1.1.12.1', [JPEGBaseline])

```

The main function *send_dicom_to_pacs()* (Listing 2) receives as input four arguments: *dicom_folder* (the path to the folder containing DICOM files), *pacs_ip* (the IP address of the PACS server), *pacs_port* (the port number of the PACS server), and *pacs_ae_title* (the AE title of the PACS server). Inside the function, an instance of *AE* is created with the AE title set to "MODALITY". The supported storage presentation contexts are set to *StoragePresentationContexts*, and a requested context for X-Ray Angiographic Image Storage is added with the UID "1.2.840.10008.5.1.4.1.1.12.1" and the transfer syntax [*JPEGBaseline*].

Listing 3: Connect to the PACS server

```

1     assoc = ae.associate(pacs_ip, pacs_port, ae_title=pacs_ae_title)
2     if assoc.is_established:
3         print('Connected to the PACS server.')

```

An association is established (Listing 3) with the PACS server using the *associate* method of the *AE* instance, binding the IP address of the PACS server, port number, and defined the AE title as arguments. Then a message is printed indicating the successful connection.

Listing 4: Iterate over DICOM files in the folder

```

1     for filename in os.listdir(dicom_folder):
2         if filename.endswith('.DCM'):
3             dicom_file = os.path.join(dicom_folder, filename)
4             # Read the DICOM file
5             dataset = dcmread(dicom_file)
6             # Send the DICOM image to the PACS server
7             status = assoc.send_c_store(dataset)
8             # Check the status of the storage request

```

```

9         if status:
10            print(f'Successfully sent {dicom_file} to the PACS ↔
                server. ')
11        else:
12            print(f'Failed to send {dicom_file} to the PACS ↔
                server. ')

```

Inside the established association, the function as presented in Listing 4 iterates over the files in the specified *dicom_folder*. If a file has the extension *.DCM*, its full path is obtained using *os.path.join*. The DICOM file is then read using *dcmread* and stored in the dataset variable. The *send_c_store* method of the association is called to send the DICOM dataset to the PACS server. The status of the storage request is checked, and appropriate messages are printed based on the success or failure of the operation.

Listing 5: Release the association

```

1         # if assoc.is_established=true then Release the association
2         assoc.release()
3         print('Disconnected from the PACS server. ')
4     else:
5         print('Failed to connect to the PACS server. ')
6 # The send_dicom_to_pacs main function finishes

```

After processing all the DICOM files, the association is released (Listing 5) using the release method, and a message is printed indicating the disconnection from the PACS server. If the association couldn't be established in the first place, a message is printed indicating the failure to connect to the PACS server.

Listing 6: Usage Example

```

1 dicom_folder = r 'C:\Users\bloodraven\Desktop\02_Projects\DT\dicom '
2 pacs_ip = '192.168.0.162' # Replace with the actual IP address
3 pacs_port = 4242 # Replace with the actual port number
4 pacs_ae_title = 'ORTHANC' # Replace with the actual AE title
5
6 # Call the main function send_dicom_to_pacs
7 send_dicom_to_pacs(dicom_folder, pacs_ip, pacs_port, pacs_ae_title)

```

Listing 6 demonstrates how to use the *send_dicom_to_pacs* function. The *dicom_folder*, *pacs_ip*, *pacs_port*, and *pacs_ae_title* variables are defined with sample values. You should replace them with the actual values corresponding to your setup. Then, the function is called with these arguments to initiate the DICOM transfer process. The commented-out lines related to the TLS layer and certificate paths indicate that TLS encryption is not currently being used in this code, but could be implemented by uncommenting and modifying those lines.

5. Simulation Results and Analysis

The diagram (Figure 3) represents the simulated environment and the integration between the DICOM simulation and the PACS server. It comprises three key components: a Windows 10 machine (where the DICOM simulation is executed), an Ubuntu Virtual Machine (VM) with a Docker container as a deployment for Orthanc, and a dedicated KALI Linux machine for enabling packet sniffing. The simulation and the deployed topology can be used as a sandbox for DICOM communication security scenarios.

To ensure device identification within the local network (Figure 3), specific IP addresses are assigned for the VMs of Windows 10, Ubuntu VM and KALI Linux. The reserved IP addresses facilitate the communication and data exchange among the different components of the simulated environment.

Figure 3. The DICOM/PACS simulated environment

5.1. Setting up Orthanc to Accept data from the Modality Simulator

Within the configuration of Orthanc (*/etc/orthanc/orthanc.json*) the *"DicomModalities"* section should be changed to accept data from the specific modality. The example contains three parameters [41]:

- Application Entity Title (AET): This parameter represents the unique identifier of the remote modality. It cannot exceed 16 characters in length. In the example, *"MODALITY"* is used as the AET.
- Remote network address: This parameter specifies the IP address or hostname of the remote modality. In the example, *"192.168.0.105"* (Windows 10) is used as the address.
- TCP port number: This parameter defines the port number on which the DICOM protocol is running on the remote modality. The default port for DICOM is 104.

The configuration (Listing 7) suggests that multiple DICOM modalities can be listed under the *"DicomModalities"* section [41], each identified by a unique AET and associated with a specific network address and port number for communication.

Listing 7: Configuration options for Orthanc: Adding the DICOM modalities

```

1 "DicomModalities" : {
2   /**
3    * The first parameter is the
4    * AET of the remote modality (cannot be longer than 16
5    * characters), the second one is the remote network address,
6    * and the third one is the TCP port number corresponding
7    * to the DICOM protocol on the remote modality (usually 104).
8    */
9   // "sample" : [ "STORESCP", "127.0.0.1", 2000 ]
10  "modality" : [ "MODALITY", "192.168.0.105", 104 ]
11 }

```

5.2. Enabling SSL/TLS

Enabling TLS in Orthanc (Listing 8) involves several steps, as outlined below [41]:

1. SSL Enabled: The *"SslEnabled"* option in the configuration file should be set to true. By default, this option is initially set to false, but changing it to true is necessary to enable SSL/TLS encryption.

2. The path to the SSL certificate should be specified: The value of `"SslCertificate"` needs to be updated with the file path of the SSL certificate. It is important that the certificate file is in the PEM format and contains both the certificate and the private key.
3. (Optional) The minimum accepted SSL protocol version can be set: The introduction of the `"ssl_protocol_version"` option in Orthanc 1.8.2 allows for the specification of the minimum accepted SSL protocol version. If desired, this option can be added, with the default being the requirement of SSL 1.2. The available protocol versions and their corresponding values can be found in the documentation or configuration file.

Listing 8: SSL/TLS options for Orthanc

```

1  /**
2   * Security-related options for the HTTP server
3   **/
4   // Whether remote hosts can connect to the HTTP server
5   "RemoteAccessAllowed" : true,
6   // Whether or not SSL is enabled
7   "SslEnabled" : false,
8   // Path to the SSL certificate used by the HTTP server. The file
9   // must be stored in the PEM format, and must contain both the
10  // certificate and the private key. This option is only meaningful
11  // if "SslEnabled" is true.
12  "SslCertificate" : "certificate.pem",
13  // Sets the minimum accepted SSL protocol version
14  // (cf. "ssl_protocol_version" option of civetweb). By default,
15  // require SSL 1.2. This option is only meaningful if "SslEnabled"
16  // is true. (new in Orthanc 1.8.2)
17  **/

```

Once these changes have been made, the configuration file should be saved, and the Orthanc server needs to be restarted to implement the modifications. As a result, the HTTP server of Orthanc will be accessible over a secure TLS connection.

5.3. Validation Tests: Scenario Test Execution

Two distinct scenarios are illustrated in Listing 9 from the script outputs. The scenarios depict different outcomes related to the transfer of data to a PACS server for validation purposes of this research.

Listing 9: Validation tests

```

1  # Scenario 1: Successful transfer – Output of the successful connection
2  C:\Users\bloodraven\Desktop\02_Projects\DT>python dicom.py
3  Connected to the PACS server.
4  Successfully sent C:\Users\bloodraven\Desktop\02_Projects\DT\dicom↵
   \0002.DCM to the PACS server.
5  Disconnected from the PACS server.
6
7  # Scenario 2: Incorrect IP or Port Number – Output of failed connection
8  C:\Users\bloodraven\Desktop\02_Projects\DT>python dicom.py
9  Failed to connect to the PACS server.

```

Upon initiating the script execution (Listing 9), the command prompt confirms a successful connection establishment with the PACS server. This connection allows subsequent data transmission. Specifically, the output informs that the file `"0002.DCM"` is located at the specified path. Similarly, in Scenario 2, the output reveals the inability to establish the intended connection, indicating that an erroneous IP address or port number was specified in the script or that other network-related complications impeded the connection process.

5.4. Network Traffic Analysis: TCP/DICOM Communication Flow

This section provides the mathematical model that describes the progression of the TCP/DICOM communication flow of the DICOM Communication. Moreover, the Listings 10-13 shows the progression of the TCP/DICOM communication flow between the DICOM modality and the PACS server.

5.4.1. Association Initialization

At the start of the communication, the MODALITY entity initiates the process by sending an A-ASSOCIATE request to Orthanc, indicating its intention to establish a DICOM association. This request occurs at time T_1 , and it is represented as equation (7):

$$MODALITY \xrightarrow{\text{A-ASSOCIATE request}} PACS \quad \text{at time } T_1 \quad (7)$$

In response to the request, Orthanc acknowledges the establishment of the association by sending an A-ASSOCIATE accept message back to MODALITY. This acceptance message occurs at time T_2 and is defined as equation (8):

$$MODALITY \xleftarrow{\text{A-ASSOCIATE accept}} PACS \quad \text{at time } T_2. \quad (8)$$

This includes the establishment of the association, data transmission, successful command execution, and the termination of the connection (Listing 10).

Listing 10: Network flow: Association Initialization

```

1 # Time|Message Type|Information|(Port Numbers)
2 T_{1} 7.633204882|A-ASSOCIATE request|DICOM: A-ASSOCIATE request ←
      MODALITY --> ORTHANC|(55822) --> (4242)
3 T_{2} 7.633597464|A-ASSOCIATE accept|DICOM: A-ASSOCIATE accept MODALITY←
      <-- ORTHANC|(55822) <-- (4242)

```

A-ASSOCIATE request: The A-ASSOCIATE request is the initial step in establishing a DICOM association between the MODALITY entity and the Orthanc entity. It is sent by the MODALITY device/system to the Orthanc device/system. The request contains information about the supported DICOM services, transfer syntaxes, and other negotiation parameters.

A-ASSOCIATE accept: The A-ASSOCIATE accept message is sent by Orthanc in response to the A-ASSOCIATE request from MODALITY. It indicates that Orthanc accepts the association. This message contains negotiated parameters, such as the agreed-upon DICOM services, transfer syntaxes, and other configuration details.

5.4.2. Data Transmission

Throughout the communication session, MODALITY sends multiple TCP segments, which are acknowledgments (ACKs), to PACS. These segments are transmitted at different times, denoted as T_3 , T_4 , and so on, representing a series of communication events as presented in equation (9):

$$MODALITY \xrightarrow{\text{TCP segments}} PACS \quad \text{at times } T_3, T_4, \dots, \quad (9)$$

where each T_i corresponds to a specific ACK transmitted by MODALITY. A sample of the data transmission in TCP segments is presented in Listing 11.

Listing 11: TCP segments in between the DICOM communication: Data transmission

```

1 # Time|Message Type|Information|(Port Numbers)
2 T_{3,4,...} **Multiple TCP flows [TCP segment of a reassembled PDU]

```

Multiple TCP flows in between (TCP segment of a reassembled PDU): The TCP segments (Listing 11) are acknowledgments (ACK) sent from the AE namely MODALITY to Orthanc, acknowledging the successful reception of a previous PDU fragment. The "S" indicates that it is a TCP segment of a reassembled PDU, suggesting that it is part of the reassembly process for the fragmented data mentioned earlier.

5.4.3. Data Reassembly and Storage

As the data transmission continues, MODALITY sends P-DATA messages, specifically C-STORE-RQ (C-STORE request) messages, to Orthanc for the purpose of storing DICOM objects. Orthanc receives and reassembles the data fragments. The reassembly events occur at times T_6 , T_7 , T_8 , and so on, forming a sequence of reception events as expressed in equation (10):

$$PACS \xrightarrow{\text{Reassembled fragments}} MODALITY \quad \text{at times } T_6, T_7, T_8, \dots, \quad (10)$$

where each T_i indicates the reception and reassembly of data fragments by Orthanc. Then, MODALITY notifies the successful execution of a command by transmitting a P-DATA message containing the relevant information, including Command ID=1 (Success), to PACS. This message is received by PACS at time, T_9 as presented in equation (11).

$$MODALITY \xleftarrow{\text{P-DATA, Command ID=1 (Success)}} PACS \quad \text{at time } T_9. \quad (11)$$

Listing 12: Data reassembly, storage and command execution

```

1 # Time|Message Type|Information|(Port Numbers)
2 **Multiple TCP flows [TCP segment of a reassembled PDU]
3
4 T_{6} 7.671284786|P-DATA, C-STORE-RQ I|DICOM: P-DATA, C-STORE-RQ ID=1|(55822) --> (4242)
5 T_{7} 7.671830832|P-DATA, X-Ray Angiog|DICOM: P-DATA, X-Ray Angiographic Image Storage Fragment (reassembled in #1394)|(55822) <- --> (4242)
6 T_{8} 7.684974645|P-DATA, X-Ray Angiog|DICOM: P-DATA, X-Ray Angiographic Image Storage|(55822) --> (4242)
7 T_{9} 7.750206628|P-DATA, Command ID=1|DICOM: P-DATA, Command ID=1 (Success)|(55822) <-- (4242)

```

P-DATA, C-STORE-RQ I: The P-DATA message is used to transfer DICOM data between the MODALITY and Orthanc entities. In this case, it is a C-STORE request (C-STORE-RQ) sent by MODALITY to Orthanc. The "ID=1" indicates that it is the first C-STORE request in the communication session. This request (Listing 12) includes information about the data to be stored, such as the DICOM object or image. A C-STORE request (C-STORE-RQ) is a DICOM message used to request the storage of DICOM objects, such as medical images, in a destination device or system. It contains information about the object to be stored, including its unique identifier and transfer syntax. The C-STORE-RQ enables the standardized and reliable transfer of DICOM objects in healthcare environments.

P-DATA, X-Ray Angiog (reassembled fragment): This message (Listing 12) represents a fragment of the X-Ray Angiographic Image Storage data. The message continues as the transmission of the X-Ray Angiographic Image Storage data continues and will reassemble in a final P-DATA network packet. It signifies that the data transmission is ongoing, and more fragments are being sent to complete the image or object.

PDATA, Command ID=1 (Success): This message (Listing 12) represents a complete DICOM P-DATA message containing the entire X-Ray Angiographic Image Storage. It indicates that the data transmission for this particular object or image is complete.

5.4.4. Association Termination

To conclude the communication, MODALITY initiates the termination process by sending an A-RELEASE request to Orthanc at time T_{10} expressed in equation (12).

$$MODALITY \xrightarrow{\text{A-RELEASE request}} PACS \quad \text{at time } T_{10}. \quad (12)$$

PACS responds by acknowledging the request with an A-RELEASE response, which is received by MODALITY at time T_{11} presented in equation (13).

$$MODALITY \xleftarrow{\text{A-RELEASE response}} PACS \quad \text{at time } T_{11}. \quad (13)$$

Listing 13: Association termination

```

1 # Time|Message Type|Information |(Port Numbers)
2 T_{10} 7.755639129|A-RELEASE request|DICOM: A-RELEASE request |(55822) ←
   --> (4242)
3 T_{11} 7.755860145|A-RELEASE response|DICOM: A-RELEASE response |(55822)←
   <-- (4242)

```

A-RELEASE request: The A-RELEASE request is sent by MODALITY to initiate the termination (Listing 13) of the DICOM association between MODALITY and Orthanc. It indicates the intention to close the connection gracefully. A-RELEASE is a message used in the DICOM protocol to initiate the termination of a DICOM association between two devices or systems. The A-RELEASE message is sent by one entity to the other, indicating the intention to gracefully close the connection. Upon receiving the A-RELEASE message, the recipient entity acknowledges the request by sending an A-RELEASE response. The A-RELEASE process allows for the orderly termination of the DICOM association, ensuring the proper release of resources and connections associated with the session. It is an essential step in maintaining the integrity and efficiency of DICOM communication between devices or systems in healthcare environments.

A-RELEASE response: The A-RELEASE response is sent by Orthanc in response to the A-RELEASE request from MODALITY. It acknowledges the termination request and signifies the successful termination of the DICOM association.

5.5. Discussion

The simulated environment for DICOM communication serves as a platform for testing and addressing essential aspects of network security and related cybersecurity issues. The environment is designed to replicate DICOM communication scenarios and facilitates a comprehensive understanding of potential threats, as well as the actions needed to mitigate them. DICOM communication is susceptible to several cyberthreats, and the simulation can assist in conducting security assessments and implement test mitigation actions in an isolated environment and realistic environment. The cyberthreats that are selected as important and can be replicated within the simulation are as follows:

1. Insecure Communication: Without encryption, sensitive DICOM data transmitted over the network is vulnerable to eavesdropping and unauthorized access.
2. Weak Authentication: Insufficient user authentication mechanisms can lead to unauthorized users gaining access to DICOM systems, compromising data integrity.
3. Outdated Software: Running outdated DICOM software components can expose vulnerabilities that malicious actors can exploit for unauthorized access or data manipulation.
4. Insufficient Training: Lack of user awareness and training can result in successful social engineering attacks, leading to unauthorized data access.
5. Unprotected Network: Failure to segment and secure the network exposes DICOM systems to potential breaches from unauthorized network traffic.

6. Data Manipulation: Without proper integrity checks, attackers might manipulate DICOM data during transmission, leading to compromised diagnoses or treatments.
7. Unauthorized Access: Poorly managed access control can result in unauthorized users gaining entry to DICOM resources.
8. Lack of Intrusion Detection: The absence of intrusion detection mechanisms makes it challenging to detect and respond to unauthorized network activities.
9. Auditing and Weakness Identification (M1047): It's crucial to perform regular audits and scans on DICOM systems to identify weaknesses that could compromise communication security.

Similarly, OWASP has also published a comprehensive guide to the secure deployment of medical devices [48]. Furthermore, in [49], a CSRF vulnerability for ORTHANC was presented. Similarly, Nmap Scripting Engine (NSE) scripts have been published related to DICOM [50,51]. These scripts aim to perform brute force attacks on the AET of a DICOM server

Table 2 outlines a set of MITRE mitigation actions along with their relevance to DICOM communication security. Each MITRE ID corresponds to a specific mitigation action designed to address a particular security concern in the context of DICOM communication.

MITRE ID	Mitigation Action	Realization and Relevance to DICOM
M1047	Perform audits or scans to identify weaknesses.	Regularly audit DICOM systems, configurations, and permissions to identify potential vulnerabilities that could impact DICOM communication.
M0804	Require user authentication.	Implement strong user authentication mechanisms before granting access to DICOM data or devices to prevent unauthorized access or data manipulation.
M1041	Encrypt Sensitive Information.	Apply strong encryption to sensitive DICOM data to ensure its confidentiality during transmission and storage.
M1051	Update Software.	Regularly update DICOM software components to patch vulnerabilities and reduce the risk of exploitation during communication.
M1017	User Training.	Train users involved in DICOM communication to recognize and respond to potential access or manipulation attempts, such as spearphishing or social engineering attacks.
M0930	Network Segmentation.	Segment the network to isolate critical DICOM systems from other network segments, preventing unauthorized access and protecting DICOM communication from potential threats.
M0931	Network Intrusion Prevention.	Use intrusion detection techniques that don't disrupt real-time DICOM communication protocols to identify and block unauthorized or malicious network traffic.
M1037	Limit Access to Resources Over Network.	Restrict network access to DICOM file shares and remote access points, reducing exposure to potential attackers and ensuring secure communication.
M1035	Filter Network Traffic.	Utilize network appliances and endpoint software to filter incoming and outgoing DICOM network traffic, blocking potentially harmful or unauthorized data flows.

Table 2. MITRE Mitigation Actions and Relevance to DICOM

In respect to guide from OWASP, the vulnerabilities and threats mentioned above, Table 2 provides the mitigation actions by MITRE that correspond to the abovementioned security issues. According to MITRE [52], mitigations embody security principles and categories of technologies that can be employed to thwart the successful execution of a technique or sub-technique. Therefore, the information of Table 2 can be used to identify other potential cyberthreats by looking to the relevant MITRE ATT&CK Navigator Layer according to each of the mitigations.

The DICOM simulation featured in this research provides valuable insights into addressing potential cybersecurity vulnerabilities and implementing corresponding miti-

gation strategies. However, it is crucial to acknowledge certain inherent limitations and constraints associated with the simulation's findings. The simulation's results are contingent upon a series of assumptions and simplifications made during the modeling phase. These assumptions might not always align with the intricacies of real-world scenarios, introducing the potential for variations that could impact the accuracy of the conclusions derived from the simulation.

Furthermore, the simulation did not involve the actual execution of cyberattacks or vulnerability assessments. This omission is attributed to the reliance on specific deployment parameters, making it difficult to accurately replicate authentic cyberattack scenarios. Consequently, the simulation's representation of real-world cyberattacks may lack the full complexity and nuanced intricacies, potentially influencing the realism of its findings.

Moreover, the simulation's scope might not encompass the entirety of potential cyberthreats. The rapidly evolving landscape of cybersecurity introduces the possibility of emerging and sophisticated threats that were not explicitly accounted for in the simulation. This limitation is a result of the inherent challenge of predicting and accommodating the myriad attack vectors that can emerge over time.

6. Conclusion

In this research, a DICOM simulator was developed within a virtual lab context, incorporating advanced features of the virtualized environments and cloud computing. The focus of the study was on conducting in-depth analyses and facilitating learning related to the fundamental attributes of the DICOM protocol. The DICOM simulator provides a flexible approach that can be further developed and customized to meet the specific needs of researchers. By utilizing cloud computing capabilities, the simulator can emulate complex scenarios and facilitate interoperability between different systems and devices. This enables researchers to explore and experiment with various aspects of DICOM communication and PACS integration. Moreover, the simulation has the capability to produce network traffic through the utilization of the DICOM protocol. This traffic generation results in the creation of authentic datasets, which can be effectively employed for the advancement of machine learning, deep learning technologies, and anomaly detection techniques.

The topology and deployment can serve as a platform for conducting security control testing. This allows researchers to evaluate the robustness of security measures, identify vulnerabilities, and test different security configurations in a controlled and safe environment. Therefore, it provides researchers with the opportunity to gain a comprehensive understanding of DICOM communication and its practical implementation.

6.1. Future Work

A significant future milestone involves fostering enhanced interoperability not only between PACS but also encompassing other medical imaging devices or formats. This expanded interoperability will facilitate seamless communication and data exchange across various SOP classes, extending the simulation support to encompass a wider range of scenarios and medical imaging modalities. Moreover, an area of promising exploration is the extension of research in the development and utilization of digital twins for medical imaging modalities. The development and utilization of digital twins for replicating healthcare or medical modalities can unlock a multitude of possibilities.

Finally, an important focus of future research involves addressing cyberthreats, conducting security assessments, creating a readily deployable topology (cyber range), and developing adversary emulation strategies aligned with the threats that were mentioned in this research.

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